

Effect of Gender Discrimination on Interpersonal and Organizational Deviance with Mediating role of Lack of Trust

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: September 17, 2021</p> <p>Accepted: April 19, 2022</p> <p>Keywords : Gender-Discrimination, Trust, Deviance, Organization</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.6473558</p>	<p><i>The purpose of this is to study scrutinizes the dispute of gender discrimination, and how discriminated female employees incline towards interpersonal and organizational deviance. With quantitative approach, the data is collected through close-ended questionnaires on the adopted instruments of the sample size of 332, and these questionnaires were distributed among female employees working in public organizations. Structural equation modelling was performed to test the multi path regression analysis by using Smart-PLS software. Results show that there is impact of gender discrimination on both, interpersonal deviance and organizational deviance, where as lack of trust plays mediating role in these relations. The study recommends devising more surveillance plans to hamper gender discrimination as it creates menace, in the shape of drastic deviance, in social and organizational set up.</i></p>

Introduction

If someone is treated worse than how you have been treated, it is direct discrimination. Basically, there are seven grounds for discrimination according to the Discrimination Ombudsman: gender, gender expression or identity, religion, ethnicity, or other beliefs, disability, age, and sexual orientation. For that to be considered discrimination, the way in which one is treated must be linked to one of the above grounds for discrimination. In addition to direct discrimination, there is indirect discrimination, such as a lack of availability, harassment, sexual harassment, and instructions to discrimination. (Azmat & Petrongolo, 2014) gender-discrimination has serious implications not just for the employee but for the workplace as a whole; employees might engage in deviant behavior against the organization as protest or revenge (Qu, Guelph, Jo, & Choi, 2017). Researchers have begun to examine gender differences in the experience of occupational stress. Although some of that research suggests that women confront certain stressors (e.g., harassment and discrimination) more often than men (Webster, Adams, Maranto, & Beehr, 2018). Dirty politics (NPITs) lead to threat appraisable employees, which result in negative emotional activation. Men and women may not be exposed differentially to political behavior in their organization, but women cognitively appraise such behaviors more negatively (i.e., as a greater threat) than men and thus have stronger emotional responses to them (Webster et al., 2018).

Gender-discrimination exists in various departments of management when it comes to working allocations, promotions, salaries, wages, decision making (Mathur, 2018) and it is revealed that females, at workplace, are being victimized of gender-discrimination due to which they do divert from their aim of working and start neglecting to follow boss's instructions, litter work environment, intentionally work slower than they could have worked, curse people at work, act rudely, and other voluntary behavior like that- that is called workplace deviance (R. J. Bennett & Robinson, 2000). In a traditionally male-dominated workplace, gender discrimination creates difficulties for women (Heilman & Caleo, 2018). Females at the workplace get diverted from their aim of working when they have been victimized of gender-discrimination (Robinson & Bennett, 1995). Putting fewer efforts in work, taking leaves, not doing work efficiently and all those behaviors that cause inequality on the workplace (Appelbaum, Iaconi, & Matousek, 2007). When one performs volitional behavior or behavior through which norms are violated, it threatens the well-being of an organization and other workers of that organization. That behavior is workplace deviance (Guay et al., 2016). Workplace deviance violates significant organizational norms, and those norms consist of basic moral standard and other traditional community standards prescribed by formal or informal organizational procedure, policies, and rules (Lee & Allen, 2002). Gender-discrimination can affect the mentality of women, which can divert them from the moral and traditional community standards. One of the important issues that are caused by the gender-discrimination on the workplace is deviant behavior (Qu, Guelph, Jo, & Choi, 2017).

Objective

The aim of the study is to find out the impact of gender discrimination on interpersonal and organizational deviance among the female employees of public sector organizations with mediating impact of lack of trust.

2.Literature Review and Hypotheses

Gender discrimination in the workplace is said to be an unjust or damaging treatment in employment activities including hiring, pay, benefits, promotion opportunities, and performance evaluation to the individuals of a certain gender group (Qu et al., 2017). Employees get indulged in counterproductive behaviors whenever they face discrimination, whether because of their gender, ethnicity, or race, against the organization they are working for as a form of protest. In corporate life, workplace deviance behavior has become a major issue (Tuclea & Filip, 2015). The situation of distrust in the individuals and organization is exacerbated when employees meet psychological contract violation or become aware of decreased level of fairness that reduces their trust in colleagues and leaders and eventually affects employee attitude and behavior and ultimately causes workplace deviance (Zheng, Wu, Chen, & Lin, 2017a).

2.1 Gender discrimination

In schooling, the Gender gap is dismissed, but in the majority of the prosperous countries, there still is a disparity in pay and level of employment according to gender. The signs of differences define the extent of discrimination. (Azmat & Petrongolo, 2014) Gender discrepancy in the workplace is affected by the following factors, and these factors can be interlinked: discrimination, priority, and productivity. Discrimination can be blunt and hidden. (Gumbus & Grodzinsky, 2016)

2.2 Dominant typologies of Discrimination

Subtle and Overt Discrimination

Overt involves blunt and explicit actions of criticizing unfairly or defame a person who is their employee or a member of their social group (Cheung et al., 2016). However, subtle discrimination is a contradiction of overt discrimination. It is obscured discrimination. Some ambiguous actions that are made with the intention to harm, actions that are detected with difficulty, have a low intensity and are often unintentional (Jones, Arena, Nittrouer, Alonso, & Lindsey, 2017)

Interpersonal and formal discrimination

Formal discrimination is felonious or structurally aligned actions. Decisions like rejecting someone for a particular job because of a person's self-concept. Whereas, interpersonal discrimination includes disrespectful, discouraging, confrontational behavior in daily inter-communication.

Micro-aggressions

Daily environmental, behavioral, and verbal humiliations-indignities that show hostile, derogatory, or negative racial slights towards targeted person whether intentionally or unintentionally and these actions are categorized as Micro-assaults, (e.g., targeted person is attacked with the intention of harming him or her), Micro-insults (e.g. ungracious or disrespectful remarks on the personality of a targeted person.) (O'Brien, McAbee, Hebl, & Rodgers, 2016) and Micro-invalidations (e.g. when making others feel less of themselves or not having enough experience through certain actions) (Cheung et al., 2016).

Discrimination is a significant social problem in Pakistan as well as throughout the world. Female has to face unequal treatment throughout the world. Women are deprived of the chances of economic involvement, the accomplishment of education health, survival, and political authorization. And gender discrimination is a serious issue, and this issue should be prevented as soon as possible. And targeting individuals can cause illness, and the individual would feel depressed so, because of traumatic stress, he probably starts performing poorly using organizational resources for personal use leading high organizational costs (Lin, Tran, Lin, & Li, 2017). In the beginning of every organization that is liberal and gender neutral and policies are made to arrange jobs and training for the benefit of the organization and not to be affected by gender differences (Dashper, 2018) in an organization comparatively men, the difficulties and barriers are more pronounced for women (Welsh, Kaciak, & Minialai, 2017). It also tolls on female workers or entrepreneurs applying to get funds required for business and that mostly happens in industrialized countries (Hattab 2011; Tlaiss 2014; Welsh, Kaciak, & Mineola; 2017). Women try to avoid risk and are more attentive than men. The aversion of risk is linked with fear of failure, referring to being less confident about the success of a given task or the practice (Carter and Shaw 2006; Kwong et al. 2012). Those researchers studying discrimination explained accurately that minority status and gender discrimination, ethnic, racial, or sexual orientation grounds are associated with psychiatric symptoms and lower self-esteem (Kucharska, 2017). Williams and colleagues (1997) Kessler et al. (1999) suggest that the direct influence of discrimination mental health is comparable to that of other common life stressors. Stress because of discrimination and negative self-concept as a member of a group with fewer power accounts for the severity of actions. Gender discrimination is a crucial component of women's everyday experiences, and it plays an important role in women identity shaping and formation of self-concept (Kucharska, 2017).

Machiavellianism

Machiavellianism is a personality trait, in this trait the discriminated person has a strong desire to be the controller of others and has a continual pursuit of Interests maximization (LeBreton, Shiverdecker, & Grimaldi,

2018). Workers try to manipulate other workers in order to complete inappropriate tasks into the workplace (Appelbaum et al., 2007). People in this personality trait are prone to be engaged in deception, betrayal, and lying antisocial behaviors might not be involved. A person is self-obsessed and is interested in personal benefits (Muris, Merckelbach, Otgaar, & Meijer, 2017).

Lack of trust

The climate of distrust in the individuals and organization is exacerbated when employees meet psychological contract violation or become aware of decreased level of fairness that reduces their trust in colleagues and leaders and eventually affects employee attitude and behavior (Zheng et al., 2017a).

Workplace deviance

Workplace deviance has been a never-ending and extortionate problem since the day industrial revolution has occurred, if not so as long as people have been recruited as proxies for others. (Detert, Treviño, Burris, & Andiappan, 2007; Dunlop & Lee, 2004). When one performs volitional behavior or behavior through which norms are violated, so, that behavior threatens the well-being of an organization and other workers of that organization. That behavior is workplace deviance (Guay et al., 2016). Organizational norms that include the documented and verbal codes of conduct, rules, and regulations are identified here because deviance must be related to the specified social group rather than the system of unmitigated moral standards. Employees either target the organization or members of an organization or both for their deviant behavior. According to social control model and bonding theory of deviance, those individuals who are tied to social gatherings, or those individuals socializing or feel tied to agreement shared by everyone in an organization are obedient in compliance with laws or rules. And there are fewer chances for these individuals to be included in aberrant acts (R. J. Bennett & Robinson, 2000).

Interpersonal deviance

Interpersonal deviance can be explained as maverick behavior or acts towards people working together or counterparts (Shamsudin, Subramaniam, & Sri Ramalu, 2014). This behavior includes mocking, molest other employees, making co-workers or other employees feel embarrassed publicly, using abusive language and using belongings of other employees without asking them (Çelik, Turunç, & Begenirbas, 2011). Many of the employees have, at least once, been stolen from their employer (R. J. Bennett & Robinson, 2000)

Incivility

When a person starts behaving in an irrespectful, ungentle, and impolite manner with other employees, then workplace incivility is said to be caused. It is found at the bottom line of the continuum of the maltreatments. Violence or aggravation is not called as incivility but the absence of admiration and politeness with others. (O'Brien et al., 2016) When a person receives such remarks that prove contemptuous and cause disrespect for him from the other employee, when the employee becomes undisciplined and cause distractions during meeting, pays no attention, humiliate others, gives negative expressions and behave roughly, do not give an answer to the question that is asked, and do not ask for anything in the requesting manner or give compliment if any kind of help is done to him and try to intervene when another person shares his or her point of view (Anwar, 2011).

Aggression

Aggression at the workplace is done with the deliberate attempts of a person, the purpose behind this is to cause harm to others with whom the person is currently working, or the person has worked within the past or maybe the organization. The person aims to impose harm purposefully and causes physical, mental, and emotional injury as well (Anwar, 2011). Employees start arguing with coworkers, disrespect the seniors, and injustice behavior with other employees as well (Baron & Neuman, 1996). When the employee delivers harm personally, then it is said to be the direct aggression, and when harm produced by another person, for example, to harm the chance of employee's promotion by spreading a damaging rumor (Anwar, 2011).

Fraud

When one has a negative intention and try to make his personal gain on the cost of another person's loss. (Bonsu, Dui, Muyun, Asare, & Amankwaa, 2018) Discriminated people if they see other employees getting preferences or promotion, so they act aberrantly, some deceiving acts are done so that they could lose something of great value (Anwar, 2011).

Organizational deviance

In most of the organizations, it is found an emerging concern and critical issue. It ruins the reputation of the organization and its stakeholders like investors, suppliers, consumers, and other employees have been negatively impacted by such kind of behavior (R. J. Bennett & Robinson, 2000) When the organization mistreats its employees then they indulge into this deviant behavior. This deviance is comprised of digressive acts that focused and directed toward the organization that includes the theft of organizational resources, slowing down of work, wastage of material (R. Bennett & Marasi, 2015). A serious economic threat can be faced by an organization with the prevalence of such acts that cause deviance at the workplace (R. J. Bennett & Robinson, 2000). Employees waste the company's resources by using them for their owns during the working hours, deliberately destroying and damaging the company's apparatus stock, and purposefully making errors in work are examples of organizational deviance. (Xxx, Spring, Marasi, Bennett, & Budden, 2018). It has been

recognized by many types of researches that deviant behavior at the workplace has significant negative outcomes to the overall productiveness and potency of the organization (Patrick, 2004). The most obvious eminence of workplace deviance may include behaviors directed at organizations like thieving, robbery, hostility, skipping, maliciousness, being always late, and exerting little effort into work, also administrators or colleagues take part in the practice of ridiculing and drolling others, playing mean tricks, and acting heedless and unsympathetic (Malik & Younas, n.d). deliberately reducing the work time, leaving early, working slowly, taking more breaks and inefficient use of company resources, ignoring the rules regarding the use of company's resources, stealing from the company, all such deviant acts have been done to harm the organization (Tuclea & Filip, 2015).

Sabotage

It is considered to be as one of those misbehaviors which are proved to be of the high cost to an organization that includes the devastation and disfigurement of the important documents and data of the organization also that belong to the coworkers. Sabotage is the substantial revelation of the hostility or ferocity (Smith, 2016). Sabotage, when reaching its highest point, is a form of transgression. This can be taken as a form of mischief that involves a part of recrimination. An individual who turns towards sabotage tries or seeks to derange, dissolve, or demobilize the working place. Sabotage target is categorized into three classifications: sabotaging people, equipment, and operations. Intention to destroy the career progression, rank, and social status of a person, or to destroy the reputation of the organization where the person is working, comes in sabotaging people. While the physically destroying something involves in the sabotaging equipment or operations (Anwar, 2011).

Gender-Discrimination, not just for the employee but also for the workplace as a whole, has serious implications, as a protest or revenge employees might indulge in deviant behavior against the organization (Qu, Guelph, Jo, & Choi, 2017). when it comes to work allocation, promotions, salaries, wages, and decision making, then departments of management make decisions on gender-based discrimination (Mathur, 2018). The situation of distrust in the individuals and organization is exacerbated when employees meet psychological contract violation or become aware of decreased level of fairness that reduces their trust in colleagues and leaders and eventually affects employee attitude and behavior (Zheng et al., 2017a). This swift scan of previous literature lured us to formulate following hypotheses;

H1a. There is a positive impact of gender discrimination on interpersonal deviance.

H1b. There is a mediating role of lack of trust between gender discrimination and interpersonal deviance.

H2a. There is a positive impact of gender discrimination on organizational deviance.

H2b. There is a mediating role of lack of trust in between gender discrimination and organizational deviance.

3. Method

This study is quantitative in approach, and the survey method was used for data collection. A close-ended questionnaire was prepared with adopted instruments. Data was collected from female employees working in

public organizations. Convenient sampling approach was taken. We distributed 350 questionnaires, and we received 332 in usable maintained condition for final analysis. Our hypothesized model involves multi path relationships, so we have used the structural equation modeling technique to analyze the results. We also used a bootstrapping technique with 5000 subsamples to test the hypotheses. We have used Smart-PLS software for analysis.

4. Measurement

We measured interpersonal deviance, and organizational deviance with 7 items and 12 items, respectively, and these items were fully adopted (R. J. Bennett & Robinson, 2000). Lack of trust was measured with 5 items, and this construct, along with its all five items, was adopted (Dahling, Whitaker, & Levy, 2009). We measured gender discrimination with 9 items of discrimination (Krieger, Smith, Naishadham, Hartman, & Barbeau, 2005), the participants were asked to respond to these nine items of discrimination on the basis of gender. All the items of every construct were measured on a five-point Likert scale through a close-ended questionnaire.

5. Results

Demographics of the participants were checked, and it was found that 65% of the participants were below the age of 35, and the rest were above it. Moreover, 43% of the participants was having 3 to 4 years of experience, whereas 29% were having 5 to 7 years of experience whereas 28% were having more than 7 years of work experience.

We diagnosed the reliability and validity of all the constructs. For internal consistency, we tested Cronbach alpha and composite reliability of every construct and the values of every construct, presented in table 1, are above the standard line which 0.7. For convergent validity, we tested average variance extracted (AVE), of all constructs and it was found that AVE of all construct, presented in table 1, is also above the standard value of 0.5.

Table 1. Construct Reliability and Validity

Constructs	Cronbach-Alpha	Composite Reliability	Average Variance Extracted
Gender Discrimination	0.92	0.93	0.63
Individual Deviance	0.88	0.91	0.60
Organizational Deviance	0.09	0.92	0.79
Organizational Trust	0.93	0.95	0.497

For discriminant validity, we initially tested cross loading of all the items, and it was found that presented in table 2, every item of any construct has greater loading to its respective construct than to any other construct, which shows that each item is discriminantly valid. Moreover, we also tested the HTMT of each construct and found out, as presented in table 3, that each construct is discriminantly valid and HTMT score of each construct is below 0.9.

Table 2. Cross Loading

	GD	ID	OD	LT
GD1	0.848	0.633	0.616	0.788
GD2	0.75	0.38	0.469	0.574
GD3	0.735	0.34	0.351	0.46
GD4	0.848	0.608	0.544	0.592
GD5	0.799	0.418	0.399	0.463
GD6	0.817	0.529	0.451	0.527
GD7	0.848	0.611	0.552	0.584
GD8	0.756	0.43	0.441	0.429
GD9	0.726	0.567	0.474	0.541
ID1	0.4	0.664	0.324	0.333
ID2	0.515	0.839	0.37	0.51
ID3	0.592	0.84	0.474	0.549
ID4	0.656	0.857	0.483	0.615
ID5	0.48	0.762	0.431	0.486
ID6	0.293	0.674	0.257	0.387
ID7	0.481	0.767	0.46	0.377
OD1	0.344	0.417	0.708	0.373

OD2	0.25	0.336	0.661	0.295
OD3	0.152	0.261	0.487	0.169
OD4	0.21	0.246	0.648	0.229
OD5	0.267	0.224	0.644	0.24
OD6	0.499	0.395	0.74	0.377
OD7	0.523	0.484	0.829	0.448
OD8	0.454	0.294	0.749	0.397
OD9	0.612	0.542	0.813	0.545
OD10	0.398	0.286	0.715	0.339
OD11	0.296	0.252	0.615	0.277
OD12	0.667	0.473	0.778	0.535
LT1	0.67	0.584	0.45	0.881
LT2	0.64	0.552	0.484	0.889
LT3	0.639	0.539	0.514	0.889
LT4	0.632	0.561	0.514	0.907
LT5	0.58	0.501	0.44	0.891

Table 3. Hetrotrail-Monotrait Ratio of Correlations (HTMT)

Construct	Gender Discrimination	Individual Deviance	Organizational Deviance	Lack of Trust
Gender Discrimination				
Individual Deviance	0.676			
Organizational Deviance	0.587	0.454		
Lack of Trust	0.745	0.658	0.539	

We also tested to multicollinearity of every individual item, as to make sure that no item in our instruments is redundant or unnecessary. We found, presented in table 4 that the score o every item of all the construct is below 0.3, which confirms that there is no multicollinearity issue in our data.

Table 4. Collinearity VIF Values

Indicator	Gender Discrimination	Individual Deviance	Organizational Deviance	Lack of Trust
1	2.928	1.53	2.081	2.914
2	2.489	2.679	1.876	2.151
3	2.112	2.535	1.505	2.154
4	2.932	2.628	1.959	2.686
5	2.606	1.844	1.862	2.406
6	2.447	1.835	1.898	
7	2.041	1.912	2.598	
8	2.036		2.031	
9	2.156		2.453	
10			1.901	
11			1.686	
12			2.181	

After the primary diagnosis, we tested the hypotheses. We first tested total effects in absence of any mediator, and found, presented in table 5, that there is positive impact of gender discrimination on interpersonal deviance [$\beta = 0.65$; $t = 17.84$; $p < 0.00$], and, there is also positive impact of gender discrimination on organizational discrimination [$\beta = 0.61$; $t = 19.08$; $p < 0.00$]. Then we tested the same relations in the presence of mediator, lack of trust, and found, presented in table 6, that beta value takes a downturn in both relationships, as in case of interpersonal deviance it is [$\beta = 0.429$; $t = 6.42$; $p < 0.001$] and in case of organizational deviance, its [$\beta = 0.469$; $t = 6.90$; $p < 0.001$]. This shows that there is a partial mediating effect of lack of trust in between gender discrimination and interpersonal deviance and in between gender discrimination and organizational deviance.

Table 5. Total Effects: Results of Structural Model in the Absence of Mediator

Path	Coefficient	t-Value	Inference
H1: GD→ID	0.65	17.84	Supported
H2: GD→OD	0.61	19.08	Supported

Table 6. Path Effects: Results of Structural Model in the Presence of Mediator

Path	Path Coefficient	t-Value	Inference
H3: GD→ID	0.429	6.427	Supported
H4: GD→OD	0.469	6.904	Supported

Specific indirect effects are presented in table 7, which show that mediating effect size of lack of trust is greater in between gender discrimination and interpersonal deviance [$\beta = 0.221$; $t = 4.49$; $p < 0.001$], than organizational deviance [$\beta = 0.148$; $t = 2.72$; $p < 0.001$].

Table 7. Specific Indirect Effects

Path	Path Coefficient	t-Value	Inference
H3: GD→LT→ID	0.221	4.491	Supported
H4: GD→LT→OD	0.148	2.722	Supported

Discussion

It has been found that whenever the female employees have been victimized of Gender-Discrimination then they indulge themselves into interpersonal deviance, this study is quite similar to the previous study, when females have been victimized of gender-discrimination, they start acting rudely, litter work environment, curse at someone at workplace and all those voluntary behaviors that come into interpersonal deviance (R. J. Bennett & Robinson, 2000). However, there are also other variables as an effective relationship between interpersonal deviance, and organizational incivility is strengthened by antagonistic actions and negative reciprocity. (Wu, Zhang, Chiu, Kwan, & He, 2014), lack of trust in colleagues and leaders due to unfair behaviors at workplace affects the behavior and attitude of employees (Zheng, Wu, Chen, & Lin, 2017b) which also show the positive impact on Interpersonal deviance.

Our study found that the females, who are victimized of gender discrimination, are more likely to cause organizational deviance. The study of (Robinson & Bennett, 1995) also tells that the females get to divert from their aim of working at the workplace when they are victimized of gender discrimination, they intentionally work slower than they could have worked, act rudely, and pay no attention to boss's instructions. Likewise, the study of (Qu et al., 2017) writes that the employees victimized of gender discrimination indulge in deviant behavior against the organization. And (Dalton, Cohen, Harp, & McMillan, 2014) as well mentions the positive impact of gender-discrimination on workplace deviance. Similarly, (Schmitt, Branscombe, & Postmes, 2003) writes, discrimination has a negative impact on well being of an organization. However, Abusive supervision can also cause organization deviance (Tepper, 2000) So does organizational structure. Centralization (hierarchy of authority) causes organizational deviance (Berry, Ones, & Sackett, 2007).

Our study resulted that all those females victimized of gender discrimination, start losing organizational trust, and that lack of trust makes them indulge in deviance, both interpersonal deviance and organizational deviance. This study is analogous with the previous study when the victimized individuals come to know about the decreased level of fairness their trust gets reduced which ultimately cause them to indulge in workplace deviance (Zheng et al., 2017b). There are also other variables that cause distrust in the organization, dispositional, and situational factors that influence an individual's self-consciousness and perception of being under evaluative scrutiny in organizations (Zheng et al., 2017b). However, one of the consequences of abusive supervision is a lack of trust (Tepper, 2000).

Implications

Policymakers when come to know about the adverse impacts of gender-discrimination then they make their policies in such a way which will give equal opportunities to both male and female that would not bring any adverse effects related to the position and image of the organization. It has been said that men and women are equal and they are given equal opportunities then why the quota system has been made, and women are considered a minority, they should give equal chances, if they will be treated with justice and if they are considered equal to the men then it will definitely bring changes in their behavior which causes workplace deviance.

Conclusion and Recommendations

The research that we have conducted was intended to show the impacts of gender discrimination and workplace deviance. Through this quantitative research, we have found out that there is a positive impact of gender discrimination on workplace deviance that whenever the gender discrimination occurs, it ultimately causes organizational deviance and interpersonal deviance and that brings unhealthy impacts on an organization.

This study was limited to the Karachi city; it is recommended that further research should be done, which would cover the whole country and its different institutions. This research was limited to organizations with female leadership, so it is also recommended that the research should be done on the employees that are under the male leadership.

References

- Anwar, M. N. (2011). Gender differences in Workplace Deviant Behavior of University Teachers and Modification Techniques. *International Education Studies*, 4(1), 193–198. <https://doi.org/http://dx.doi.org/10.5539/ies.v4n1p193>
- Appelbaum, S. H., Iaconi, G. D., & Matousek, A. (2007). Positive and negative deviant workplace behaviors: Causes, impacts, and solutions. *Corporate Governance*, 7(5). <https://doi.org/10.1108/14720700710827176>
- Azmat, G., & Petrongolo, B. (2014). Gender and the labor market: What have we learned from field and lab experiments? *Labour Economics*, 30, 32–40. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.labeco.2014.06.005>
- Baron, R. A., & Neuman, J. H. (1996). Workplace violence and workplace aggression: Evidence on their relative frequency and potential causes. *Aggressive Behavior*, 22(3). [https://doi.org/10.1002/\(SICI\)1098-2337\(1996\)22:3<161::AID-AB1>3.0.CO;2-Q](https://doi.org/10.1002/(SICI)1098-2337(1996)22:3<161::AID-AB1>3.0.CO;2-Q)
- Bennett, R. J., & Robinson, S. L. (2000). Development of a measure of workplace deviance. *Journal of Applied Psychology*, 85(3), 349–360. <https://doi.org/10.1037/0021-9010.85.3.349>
- Bennett, R., & Marasi, S. (2015). Workplace Deviance. In *International Encyclopedia of the Social & Behavioral Sciences: Second Edition*. <https://doi.org/10.1016/B978-0-08-097086-8.22006-0>
- Berry, C. M., Ones, D. S., & Sackett, P. R. (2007). Interpersonal deviance, organizational deviance, and their common correlates: A review and meta-analysis. *Journal of Applied Psychology*. <https://doi.org/10.1037/0021-9010.92.2.410>
- Bonsu, O.-A. M., Dui, L. K., Muyun, Z., Asare, E. K., & Amankwaa, I. A. (2018). Corporate Fraud: Causes, Effects, and Deterrence on Financial Institutions in Ghana. *European Scientific Journal*, 14(28), 315–335. <https://doi.org/10.19044/esj.2018.v14n28p315>
- Çelik, M., Turunç, Ö., & Begenirbas, M. (2011). The role of organizational trust, burnout and interpersonal deviance for achieving organizational performance. *International Journal of Business and Management Studies*, 3(2).
- Cheung, H. K., King, E., Lindsey, A., Membere, A., Markell, H. M., & Kilcullen, M. (2016). Understanding and reducing workplace discrimination. *Research in Personnel and Human Resources Management*, 34(April 2018), 101–152. <https://doi.org/10.1108/S0742-730120160000034010>
- Dahling, J. J., Whitaker, B. G., & Levy, P. E. (2009). The development and validation of a new Machiavellianism Scale. *Journal of Management*, 35(2), 219–257. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0149206308318618>
- Dalton, D. W., Cohen, J. R., Harp, N. L., & McMillan, J. J. (2014). Antecedents and consequences of perceived gender discrimination in the audit profession. *Auditing*. <https://doi.org/10.2308/ajpt-50737>
- Dashper, K. (2018). Challenging the gendered rhetoric of success? The limitations of women-only mentoring for tackling gender inequality in the workplace. *Gender, Work and Organization*. <https://doi.org/10.1111/gwao.12262>
- Detert, J. R., Treviño, L. K., Burris, E. R., & Andiappan, M. (2007). Managerial Modes of Influence and Counterproductivity in Organizations: A Longitudinal Business-Unit-Level Investigation. *Journal of Applied Psychology*, 92(4), 993–1005. <https://doi.org/10.1037/0021-9010.92.4.993>
- Dunlop, P. D., & Lee, K. (2004). Workplace deviance, organizational citizenship behavior, and business unit performance: The bad apples do spoil the whole barrel. *Journal of Organizational Behavior*, 25(1), 67–80. <https://doi.org/10.1002/job.243>
- Guay, R. P., Choi, D., Oh, I. S., Mitchell, M. S., Mount, M. K., & Shin, K. H. (2016). Why people harm the organization and its members: Relationships among personality, organizational commitment, and workplace deviance. *Human Performance*, 29(1). <https://doi.org/10.1080/08959285.2015.1120305>
- Gumbus, A., & Grodzinsky, F. (2016). Era of big data. *ACM SIGCAS Computers and Society*, 45(3), 118–125. <https://doi.org/10.1145/2874239.2874256>
- Heilman, M. E., & Caleo, S. (2018). Combatting gender discrimination: A lack of fit framework. *Group Processes and Intergroup Relations*, 21(5), 725–744. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1368430218761587>
- Jones, K. P., Arena, D. F., Nittrouer, C. L., Alonso, N. M., & Lindsey, A. P. (2017). Subtle discrimination in the

- workplace: A vicious cycle. *Industrial and Organizational Psychology*, 10(1), 1–26. <https://doi.org/10.1017/iop.2016.91S1754942616000912>
- Krieger, N., Smith, K., Naishadham, D., Hartman, C., & Barbeau, E. M. (2005). Experiences of discrimination: Validity and reliability of a self-report measure for population health research on racism and health. *Social Science and Medicine*, 61(7), 1576–1596. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.socscimed.2005.03.006>
- Kucharska, J. (2017). Cumulative trauma, gender discrimination and mental health in women: mediating role of self-esteem. *Journal of Mental Health*, 0(0), 1–8. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09638237.2017.1417548>
- LeBreton, J., Shiverdecker, L. K., & Grimaldi, E. M. (2018). *The Dark Triad and Workplace Behavior*. SSRN. <https://doi.org/10.1002/cav.359>
- Lee, K., & Allen, N. J. (2002). Organizational citizenship behavior and workplace deviance: The role of affect and cognitions. *Journal of Applied Psychology*, 87(1), 131–142. <https://doi.org/10.1037/0021-9010.87.1.131>
- Lin, P. K., Tran, T. T., Lin, P. C., & Li, S. Y. (2017). Gender discrimination misconducts perceived by female workers of Vietnamese industries. In *14th International Conference on Services Systems and Services Management, ICSSSM 2017 - Proceedings*. <https://doi.org/10.1109/ICSSSM.2017.7996232>
- Mathur, G. (2018). Gender-Based Discrimination Faced By Females At Workplace : a Perceptual Study, 21(July), 1–7.
- Muris, P., Merckelbach, H., Otgaar, H., & Meijer, E. (2017). The Malevolent Side of Human Nature. *Perspectives on Psychological Science*, 12(2). <https://doi.org/10.1177/1745691616666070>
- O'Brien, K. R., McAbee, S. T., Hebl, M. R., & Rodgers, J. R. (2016). The impact of interpersonal discrimination and stress on health and performance for early career STEM academicians. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 7(1). <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2016.00615>
- Qu, Y., Guelph, C. ©, Jo, W., & Choi, C. (2017). Understanding workplace deviant behaviours based on perceived gender discrimination, organizational justice and organizational attachment: A case of Chinese hotel employees.
- Robinson, S. L., & Bennett, R. J. (1995). a Typology of Deviant Workplace Behaviors: a Multidimensional Scaling Study. *Academy of Management Journal*, 38(2), 555–572. <https://doi.org/10.2307/256693>
- Schmitt, M. T., Branscombe, N. R., & Postmes, T. (2003). Women's emotional responses to the pervasiveness of gender discrimination. *European Journal of Social Psychology*. <https://doi.org/10.1002/ejsp.147>
- Shamsudin, F. M., Subramaniam, C., & Sri Ramalu, S. (2014). The influence of HR practices and job satisfaction on interpersonal deviance in the workplace. *Journal of Management and Organization*, 20(5). <https://doi.org/10.1017/jmo.2014.50>
- Smith, S. (2016). Can a Code of Ethics Reduce Sabotage and Increase Productivity under Tournament-Based Compensation ? An Experimental Study.
- Tepper, B. J. (2000). Consequences of abusive supervision. *Academy of Management Journal*. <https://doi.org/10.2307/1556375>
- Țuclea, C.-E., & Filip, A. (2015). Dimensions of Deviant Workplace Behavior in Small and Medium-Sized Enterprises. *Review of International Comparative Management*, 16(1).
- Webster, J. R., Adams, G. A., Maranto, C. L., & Beehr, T. A. (2018). “Dirty” Workplace Politics and Well-Being. *Psychology of Women Quarterly*, 42(3), 361–377. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0361684318769909>
- Welsh, D. H. B., Kaciak, E., & Minialai, C. (2017). The influence of perceived management skills and perceived gender discrimination in launch decisions by women entrepreneurs. *International Entrepreneurship and Management Journal*, 13(1). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11365-015-0379-y>
- Wu, L. Z., Zhang, H., Chiu, R. K., Kwan, H. K., & He, X. (2014). Hostile Attribution Bias and Negative Reciprocity Beliefs Exacerbate Incivility's Effects on Interpersonal Deviance. *Journal of Business Ethics*. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10551-013-1658-6>
- Zheng, W., Wu, Y. C. J., Chen, X. C., & Lin, S. J. (2017a). Why do employees have counterproductive work behavior? The role of founder's Machiavellianism and the corporate culture in China. *Management Decision*, 55(03). <https://doi.org/10.1108/MD-10-2016-0696>
- Zheng, W., Wu, Y. C. J., Chen, X. C., & Lin, S. J. (2017b). Why do employees have counterproductive work behavior? The role of founder's Machiavellianism and the corporate culture in China. *Management Decision*. <https://doi.org/10.1108/MD-10-2016-0696>

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